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THE ROLE OF ENVIRONMENTAL GREENING IN STRATEGIC PERFORMANCE OF UNIVERSITIES*

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Abstract

Given the growing environmental challenges, environmental greening has become a crucial goal for universities, serving as a primary driver for societal development across various sectors. Universities face the significant challenge of balancing their academic responsibilities with environmental conservation, ensuring that their actions do not adversely impact natural resources. Despite the importance of this issue, few studies have explored the relationship between university responsibilities and environmental sustainability from a strategic perspective. This study aims to explore the views of university leadership on the key responsibilities that universities must undertake to achieve environmental greening and to assess how effectively these responsibilities are being met. This descriptive survey study employed the Delphi method, targeting a purposeful sample of 25 professors to identify the most critical responsibilities for environmental greening. Additionally, a broader sample of 176 university leaders was surveyed to evaluate the extent to which these responsibilities are being fulfilled. The study identified 29 key responsibilities that universities should adopt to promote environmental greening. Findings indicate that the university's efforts in exercising these responsibilities are moderate but generally lean towards being weak.

Keywords: environmental greening, strategy, sustainability, performance, universities

1. Introduction

Universities have served as catalysts for social transformation. As large employers and consumers of goods and services, universities help to educate most of the world's most important people (such as presidents, CEOs, and teachers), but they also play an essential economic role. Universities are being asked more and more to help solve problems like climate change and environmental and sustainability because of their social and economic value. Their duty is to educate and inform people on how to live more sustainably. The engines of sustainable

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development include education, research, and knowledge transmission. Universities have a lot more to do than just teach undergraduate and graduate students. They also have to deal with campus administration, operations, purchasing, transportation, and community involvement. Universities are realizing they can educate and demonstrate sustainability by identifying and mitigating their own unsustainable consequences. Students studying sustainability might create a "shadow curriculum" in which theory and practice are woven together (Leal Filho, 2000; Smith, 1993; Souhli and En-nadi, 2023).

However, there is evidence that many universities are dealing with the notion and aim of "greening," with dispersed and unsystematic outcomes. It is important to distinguish between a project's success and a systemic transformation that is more sustainable (Puspitasari et al., 2022; Sharp, 2013). However, colleges must address sustainability from both extrinsic and intrinsic perspectives. This should encourage universities to pursue sustainable/green university practices.

To achieve sustainable development, education has been considered humanity's greatest chance (United Nations Educational, 1997). In this setting, universities must help define and model best practices. The constant development of higher education in countries has spawned a new set of conflicting demands. Among them is sustainability. The most effective green campus projects understand shifting objectives and welcome new possibilities created by expansion and development (Sharp, 2013). While there are notable examples of university sustainability projects across the world, it is critical to encourage their replication on as many campuses as possible.

It has recently become more important to pay attention to environmental issues because of the negative effects of pollution on people. International organizations, associations, and states have called for the protection of the environment from pollution and the rationalization of the use of its natural resources. Environmental management specifications have been developed, including British specifications, EU specifications, ISO specifications, and the latter is the most widespread across the world, and the application of this system is being given increased attention, particularly by the organizations of developed countries, where the category of green customers is growing, given the advantages that its application provides in various areas. On the other hand, adopting such a system is thought to be the best thing that businesses can do to improve their strategic performance. This study shows how the environmental management system is linked to this performance from this point of view.

2. Literature review

In order to become "green institutions," several universities focused their efforts on making changes to their campus layout, architecture, administration, and operations. This has been investigated by a number of researchers .

According to Suwartha and Sari (2013), the UI Green Metric system creation and application were detailed using the findings of the 2011 ranking in order to gauge current situations and policies relating to green campus development and sustainable development in universities all over the world. More nations have joined since 2001, as well as a growing focus on energy and climate change problems at several colleges. The UI Green Metric ranking measures each institution's performance in promoting green universities and long-term growth, say the developers of the UI Green Metric ranking.

Ranking methods for worldwide universities' sustainability are divided and underused, according to Shi and Lai (2013), since sustainability is a subjective concept and aim for universities and there is no universally approved evaluation technique and criteria. For the top 100 QS ranking universities, they came up with a different way to measure sustainability. They came up with a well-structured and clear criterion tree to use. The greening performance of institutions throughout the globe was assessed using macro level methodologies by different authors. Some scientists developed a micro-level measurement technique for sustainability in the

context of a case study of an Indian institution in Brazil (de Castro and Jabbour, 2013; Suwartha and Sari, 2013; Shi and Lai, 2013). It was found that the sustainable development activities of an Indian university matched up with the factors specified by the framework they employed to examine how higher educational institutions contribute to sustainable development (Alshuwaikhat and Abubakar, 2008). A viable framework for examining University Alpha's sustainability activities was established.

From several stakeholders' viewpoints (Yuan et al., 2013), Shandong University in China was the subject of an investigation into the most significant variables that contribute to the achievement of Green University goals. Students' parents, alumni, and faculty members were surveyed in a large-scale questionnaire poll about their views on the impact of sustainable development on the growth of green institutions. The researchers wrote that students' parents and faculty were less concerned about environmental concerns than graduates, and all three groups were unaware of the Green University in relation to their overall understanding of environmental issues, the researchers wrote.

There needs to be a greater understanding by academic leaders of the importance of business schools in the development of the next generation of leaders and entrepreneurs. Examples of green business schools in Brazil: Two real-life cases (de Castro and Jabbour, 2013) Sustainable development was a major focus of their business school's teaching and research. According to the authors, sustainable development management was a top priority for academics. Environmental management is difficult for business schools, even if they are considered intellectual leaders. An important challenge for business schools is to include environmental management within their curriculum.

Geng et al., (2013) offered China's "green university" case study. In collaboration with Shenyang University, they created an integrated green campus model. According to the researchers, Green Shenyang environmental management may be easily integrated into the administration of business schools as a result of these findings.

According to a statement made by Wang et al., (2013). It is our hope that these and other important difficulties in the construction and implementation of green institutions will inspire future research to solve these and other urgent issues. It is impossible to have a green society without the leadership of green universities, and green universities can't be called green universities unless they help their local communities grow.

3. Methodology

3.1. The problem of study

The primary issue in this research is indicated by the following fundamental question, which is based on the benefits and effects of environmental greening at the university level: ***As a way to improve the strategic performance of universities, how can environmental greening be used?***

In order to understand all aspects of the main question, the following sub-questions were asked:

- What's an environmental greening system, and what are its types?
- What is strategic performance and what are its dimensions?
- What elements of strategic performance can environmental greening affect?
- What benefits have universities achieved as a result of their application of environmental greening?

3.2. The significance of the research

This research is based on the topic that is one of the most current themes in the world of educational institutions, which is the subject of environmental greening systems. As a result, educational institutions have realized the need to incorporate environmental greening into their operations in order to achieve their goals with the greatest efficiency and effectiveness possible, which is reflected favorably in their strategic performance. To find out how environmental greening helps universities improve their strategic performance, this study will look at the case of Samarra University.

3.3. Aims of the research

This study aims at:

- Identification of the conceptual framework of the environmental greening system.
- Determine some fundamental concepts of strategic performance.
- To highlight the actual practice of the environmental greening system at the university level.
- Exploring the reality of environmental greening in one of Iraq's universities, namely Samarra University, and highlighting its implications for its strategic performance.
- Make recommendations that would contribute to ensuring the practical and correct application of the environmental greening system at Iraqi universities in general and Samarra University in particular.

3.4. Study approach

In view of the nature and objectives of the study, the analytical descriptive approach was drawn upon for in-depth study and comprehensive analysis of the contribution of the environmental greening system to the development of the strategic performance of **Samarra University**, through data obtained from sources and references, as well as data obtained from the university in question.

4. Theoretical concept

4.1. Environmental greening

Greening: is the process of making living surroundings, as well as artifacts such as a place, a lifestyle, or a brand image, more ecologically friendly (for example, "greening your house" or "greening your office"). Greening is the process of making one's environment, like one's home, workplace, and way of life, more environmentally friendly (Zhu et al., 2016).

Among "green" characteristics are, but are not limited to: toxicity is lessened; re-usability; efficiency in terms of energy; packaging and labeling that are environmentally friendly; recyclable materials; clever design; and environmentally friendly production procedures; personal environmental dangers are reduced, reducing the heat effect.

4.1.1. The conceptual framework of the environmental greening system

Greening programs, as well as exposure to them, have been shown to provide significant health advantages for individuals of all ages. Greening can help relieve the stress of living in an urban area by giving people more places to be alone, cutting down on noise, and making the air cooler (Forsyth and Peiser, 2021). Greening activities may have a positive impact on both physical and mental health, as well as increase environmental consciousness. Habitat restoration, tree planting, food gardening, and naturalization are all examples of greening (Mousa and Puhakka, 2019).

Adopting techniques that might help them deal with environmental issues and pursue new opportunities is becoming increasingly popular among businesses. Increased demand for ecologically friendly products and services; greater public expectations for companies to meet their environmental responsibilities, and more stringent regulations are just a few of the factors driving companies to go green. The competitive landscape will be altered in unexpected ways as a result of environmental concerns. For example, the stock value of companies that do not address environmental concerns is being driven down by investors. The environmental records and goals of an organization are becoming increasingly important to customers when they decide to buy, lease, or outsource. A rising number of investors are interested in green projects and in developing and promoting green products and services. According to government officials, investors, and the general public, companies must publish more information about their carbon footprint, environmental initiatives, and successes. Companies that have the technology and vision to manufacture environmentally friendly products and services will have a competitive advantage (Lash and Wellington, 2007).

4.1.2. The actual practice of the environmental greening system

The most prominent strategic environmental plans needed to achieve environmental greening are:

- 1) Protection and improvement of air quality includes six environmental axes: air pollution as a result of natural factors, air pollution from stationary industrial sources, air pollution from moving industrial sources, noise, inspection, measurement, and surveillance, and clean energies. If the institution can meet this goal, it will be a big help in making the world a better place.
- 2) Protection and improvement of water quality: It covers four environmental axes: water needs, sustainable and integrated water resource management, and waste water. If the institution were able to achieve this strategic objective, it would be effective in achieving sustainable development.
- 3) Reducing land degradation and combating desertification: It contains four environmental axes: land use, desertification, soil pollution, and natural vegetation. If the institution could meet this goal, it would be very good at achieving sustainable development.
- 4) Conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity includes five environmental axes: conservation of local neighborhood specimens, sustainability of ecosystems, institutional and legal frameworks, environmental education, and public participation. If the institution can meet this strategic goal, it will be able to help people have a better future.
- 5) Development and improvement of waste management: It contains two environmental axes, namely, non-hazardous wastes and hazardous wastes. If the institution can meet this strategic goal, it will be able to help people have a better future.
- 6) Reduction of radioactive contamination includes five environmental axes: knowledge and communication management, radioactive contaminated sites, transport of radioactive material, depleted uranium, and radioactive contingency plans. If the foundation is able to achieve this strategic objective, it will be instrumental in achieving sustainable development.
- 7) Integrated management of hazardous chemicals includes three environmental areas: accounting for and rectification of hazardous chemicals; accounting for and disposal of chemical residues resulting from various activities; and control of the circulation of toxic and hazardous chemicals. If the institution can meet this strategic goal, it will be able to help people have a better future.
- 8) Development of the institutional and legal framework for the environmental sector: It includes three environmental axes: legislation and policy; human resources; education; and environmental information. If the institution can meet this strategic goal, it will be able to help people have a better future.

4.2. Basic concepts of strategic performance

The topic of strategic performance is central to theories of organizational behavior in general and administrative management in particular, given the importance it represents in achieving the objectives of institutions of all kinds, of which educational institutions are one. From this point of view, some basic concepts of strategic performance will be addressed in terms of their concepts, dimensions, and foundations.

4.2.1. Strategic performance concept

Strategic performance has been defined by many definitions, the most important of which are:

- The extent to which the foundation has achieved its strategic objectives, which in turn reflect different economic, social, and environmental needs (Tarigan and Siagian, 2021).
- It is a reflection of the organization's ability to meet its internal (such as resource) and external environmental requirements (such as customer satisfaction and loyalty and social responsibility) in the near and long term compared to competitors in adopting specific strategies (Govindan et al., 2015).
- It is the result of all the different strategic processes and phases that serve as the strategic management mirror of the organization (Elia et al., 2017).

From previous definitions, it can be said that strategic performance is the extent to which the organization has achieved its strategic objectives, which in turn are far-reaching.

4.2.2. Strategic performance dimensions

Strategic performance is very important to the success of an organization and its ability to meet its strategic goals. This performance has the following dimensions:

- 1) *Operational dimension*: This dimension assumes operational performance measures through market share and the introduction of a new product, as well as with respect to customer value added, innovation, and process improvement (Achrol and Kotler, 2012).
- 2) *Social dimension*: or what some call the satisfaction of stakeholders, i.e. performance that takes into account the satisfaction of stakeholders from workers, processors, customers, society... etc. (Achrol and Kotler, 2012)
- 3) *Economic dimension*: It's both the productive and the service side, the marketing side, and the financial side.
- 4) *Societal dimension*: Both the society in which the enterprise is active and the demands of workers and trade unions represent the client side.
- 5) *Environmental dimension*: includes material and water consumption, energy consumption, and environmental pollution.

Based on the above considerations, Fig. 1 shows how strategic performance is broken down.

4.2.3. Foundations for strategic performance

Strategic performance builds on a set of foundations or rules:

- 1) *Mission Statement*: These are the unique characteristics of the organization and distinguish them from other similar organizations, and this statement reflects the mental image that the organization wishes to project on the minds of individuals (AlQatamin, 2002).

- 2) *Principles*: are everything related to the ideas and beliefs shared by individuals and guide their behavior to achieve harmony that reflects the efficiency of the institution (Grigoroudis et al., 2012). such as:
 - To move towards the desired objectives.
 - Collective action.
 - Mastering work.
- 3) *Vision*: It's the future situation that the organization wants to reach. It's an ambition, a desire, and a challenge all at once (O'Shannassy, 2003).
- 4) *Strategic Objectives*: These are outcomes that the organization seeks to achieve that are directly linked to its vision 26. In other words, after the organization has set out its long-term goals, it lays out the steps it will take to get there.
- 5) The strategy is a set of decisions and activities chosen to achieve long-term objectives.

Fig. 1. Strategic performance dimensions

5. Field study

5.1. Curriculum and tools for research

The current research was based on the descriptive and survey curriculum, where the researcher surveyed the views of university leaders through the Delphi method on the most important responsibilities of Samarra University towards environmental greening, and then prepared an identification to determine the degree to which these responsibilities were actually exercised.

5.2. The research community and the sample

The research community is represented by all the academic and administrative leaders at the University of Samarra. As for the research sample that the Delphi method was applied to, it was a deliberate sample of 25 university leaders. As for the sample on which the questionnaire was applied, it was a coincidental sample consisting of 176 university leaders.

5.3. Presentation and interpretation of the results of the field study

5.3.1. The results of figuring out what the university's most important roles are for sustainability and greening the environment

In order to determine the university's main educational responsibilities for achieving environmental greening, the researcher directed the Delphi method to a deliberate sample of 25 professors from university leaders. In its initial form, Delphi may consist of one open question about the roles or responsibilities expected from the university to achieve sustainability and environmental greening. That is, providing useful information and experience in the field of environmental sustainability to be used in answering the open question. After collecting the responses from the first round of Delphi, these responses were arranged and categorized according to the responsibilities of the university (university administration, the educational process, scientific research, and community service) in order to direct them to the same sample in the second round to determine the degree of their agreement on the importance of the responsibilities. Barely (20) professors from the selected sample responded in this round. In order to adopt the Delphi method, the researcher determined that 75% was for each paragraph on which the views of the sample were agreed or met, as explained by (Plake, 2008), who emphasized that the Delphi method could be relied upon if it was not less than 75% approved. In this round, the researcher has only reached approval ratings of 76.8% to 92.6%, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Arithmetic averages and percentage degrees of approval of the Delphi method sample for the most important responsibilities of Samarra University for environmental sustainability

No.	Indicators	Arithmetic Av.	Percentage
The University's responsibilities for environmental sustainability			
A.	University management responsibility towards sustainability and environmental greening		
1.	Working to turn the university into a green campus.	4.63	92.6
2.	Allocation of a financial budget for the management of sustainability and environmental greening at the University	4.63	92.6
3.	Establishment of a Special Office for Sustainability and Environmental Greening at the University to coordinate and support environmental sustainability initiatives and projects within and outside the University.	4.58	91.6
4.	Development and electronic availability of a database on sustainability and environmental greening issues.	4.47	89.4
5.	Establish communication channels within and outside the University to manage environmental sustainability.	4.42	88.4
6.	Clear policy (strategic plan) on sustainability and environmental greening	4.37	87.4
7.	The establishment of an agency in every college for sustainability and environmental greening.	3.84	76.8
B.	Responsibility for university education towards sustainability and environmental greening		
8.	Take advantage of the programs of the continuing education system to graduate professionals qualified for sustainability and environmental greening.	4.47	89.4
9.	Linking academic programmes in sustainability and environmental greening with field training in relevant community institutions	4.47	89.4
10.	Standards for the quality and adoption of academic programmes include indicators for sustainability and environmental greening.	4.42	88.4
11.	Use international experts in the shift towards education for sustainability and environmental greening.	4.42	88.4

12.	Connecting sustainability and environmental greening programs to the community of practice; transforming the campus into a learning and application laboratory for sustainable environmental practices	4.42	88.4
13.	Linking the values and issues of sustainability and environmental greening to relevant academic programs.	4.37	87.4
14.	Introduction of an academic course (university requirement) on sustainability and environmental greening	4.11	82.2
15.	Academic disciplines (at various university levels) in sustainability and environmental greening are being introduced.	4.05	81
C.	University scientific research responsibility towards sustainability and environmental greening		
16.	Implementation of developmental studies and research for community services and human well-being	4.58	91.6
17.	Providing participatory research grants between local and international universities to address sustainability and environmental greening issues.	4.53	90.6
18.	Establishment of research and pilot incubators at the university to market environmentally sustainable research into commercial products.	4.53	90.6
19.	Establishment of research chairs supporting sustainability and environmental greening research.	4.47	89.4
20.	Establishment of the Community Research Centre to transform sustainability research into community-oriented practices.	4.47	89.4
21.	Create research maps that encourage researchers to study sustainability and environmental greening as a national priority.	4.42	88.4
22.	The allocation of certain grades of promotion to "community service" to the role of faculty members towards sustainability and environmental greening	4.16	83.2
D.	The University's societal responsibility towards sustainability and environmental greening		
23.	Building community partnerships to implement sustainability and environmental greening initiatives and projects.	4.63	92.6
24.	Benefit from community service centres in holding workshops to train university and community workers in the application of sustainable environmental practices.	4.58	91.6
25.	The establishment by the university of Citizens' Clubs "is aimed at raising their awareness of green environmental practices and meeting their environmental needs."	4.58	91.6
26.	Community competitions on sustainability and environmental greening.	4.53	90.6
27.	Providing advice in support of comprehensive sustainable development programmes and plans.	4.53	90.6
28.	Seminars and meetings aimed at educating members of society on the need for sustainability and environmental greening	4.47	89.4
29.	University and local community institution leaders are being trained in the transition to sustainability and environmental greening.	4.47	89.4

5.3.2. The results of determining the reality of the university's exercise of its responsibilities towards achieving sustainability and environmental greening

To reveal the reality of the university's exercise of its responsibilities towards sustainability and environmental greening, the researcher has drawn up a list of responsibilities resulting from the Delphi method in the questionnaire to identify this objective.

This questionnaire was first reviewed by four professors to verify its apparent validity, and after judging the validity of the questionnaire's paragraphs in revealing what it was developed for, and on the correlation of its paragraphs with the axes that fall under it, and on its clarity and soundness of wording, the validity of the content, or what is known as consistency validity, was also calculated. The internal procedure was to recognize how well the expressions represented the domain to be measured, and this was done through the alpha-Kronbach method, which is used to calculate the stability (0.852), then the validity by taking the square root of the stability (0.923). And because the degree of stability of the questionnaire as a whole was high, the degree of validity of the questionnaire was very high. The questionnaire was also presented to an exploratory sample of 15 faculty members to judge the clarity of the phrases in order to ensure a common understanding among the sample members as well as to calculate the stability of the questionnaire, which was carried out by the method of Guttman. It was found that the stability coefficient was 0.967, which is a high and reliable stability coefficient. After the questionnaire was made legal, it was sent to a random group of 176 university leaders in its final form. Table 2 shows the distribution of sample personnel by study variables after discharge of yield on resolution.

Table 2. Distribution of sample members by study variables

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Groups</i>	<i>Number</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Specialization	Islamic Science	19	10.79
	Human Sciences	104	59.09
	Natural Science	53	30.11
Leadership position	Dean	35	19.88
	Associate Dean	43	24.43
	Head of the Department	98	55.68
Degree	Professor	32	18.18
	Assistant Professor	57	32.38
	Lecturer	87	49.43

After analyzing the responses of the sample members using the following: arithmetic average, standard deviation, variance analysis (P), multiple comparisons method (LSD), through SPSS version 23, the relative weight of each response was also estimated on the questionnaire according to the five-response Likert method, as shown in Table 3.

After statistical data processing, the study found the following results:

1. The University exercises its responsibilities towards sustainability and environmental greening with an average degree (2.81), consisting of university administration with a degree (2.97), community service with a degree (2.80), educational process with a degree (2.75) and, finally, scientific research with a degree (2.72), as shown in Table 4.

2. The university's management exercises its responsibilities towards sustainability and environmental greening at an overall level (2.97). To this effect, the subparagraphs range from weak practice (2.49) to medium practice (3.30). Figure 2 illustrates this.

3. University education exercises its responsibilities towards environmental sustainability to a medium degree (2.75) overall, and the sub-paragraphs indicate that their averages ranged between the two degrees of weak practice (2.59) and medium (2.88). Figure 3 illustrates this.

Table 3. Arithmetic average partitions by response levels

<i>Answer level</i>	<i>Values of arithmetic averages</i>
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	<i>from</i>	<i>to</i>
Very low	1.00	1.80
Low	1.81	2.60
Middle	2.61	3.40
High	3.41	4.20
Very high	4.21	5

Table 4. The reality of the University's exercise of its responsibilities towards sustainability and environmental greening

<i>Axle No.</i>	<i>Axle name</i>	<i>Arithmetic Av.</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>Relative importance</i>
a	University Administration	2.97	1.003	59.4
b	University Education	2.75	0.976	55
c	Scientific Research	2.72	1.011	54.4
d	Community Service	2.80	1.052	56
	Total	2.81	0.964	56.2

Fig. 2. The reality of the university administration exercising its responsibilities towards sustainability and environmental greening

Fig. 3. The reality of university education exercising its responsibilities towards sustainability and environmental greening

4. Scientific research in university exercises its responsibilities towards environmental sustainability to a medium degree (2.72) in a general way. As for the sub-paragraphs indicating that its averages ranged between the two degrees of weak practice (2.44) and medium (2.99). Figure 4 illustrates this.

5. In general, universities exercise their societal responsibilities towards environmental sustainability to a medium degree (2.80) in general, and the sub-paragraphs indicating this ranged

in their averages between the degrees of weak practice (2.58) and medium (2.99). Figure 5 illustrates this.

6. It is clear from these four forms that all the averages of the paragraphs of the questionnaire revealing the reality of the university's exercise of its responsibilities towards environmental sustainability range between (3.30) and (2.44); that is, between (66%) and (48.8%), meaning that the university exercises its responsibilities towards environmental sustainability to a moderate degree that tends to be weak. Perhaps the explanation for this is due to the fact that the university is still at an early stage in the application of environmental sustainability, and the achievement of these practices to that degree may be due to the existence of obstacles that prevent the application of environmental sustainability, such as: university regulations restricting work, the absence of a strategic vision for environmental sustainability, the lack of motivating financial or human resources to lead the shift towards this sustainability.

Fig. 4. The reality of scientific research practicing its responsibilities towards sustainability and environmental greening

Fig. 5. The reality of the university's practice of its societal responsibilities towards sustainability and greening the environment

5.3.3. Analysis of variance (*P*) is used to see if there are statistically significant differences in the average responses of the sample members when they are asked about the study variables.

The results showed that there were no statistically significant differences between the average responses of the university leadership sample, according to variables: leadership position and degree, in identifying the disclosure of the reality of the university's exercise of its responsibilities towards environmental sustainability and greening the environment as a whole. This means consistent responses from the university leadership sample and the lack of influence of any of the variables. This result can also be attributed to administrative centralization, which

limits the ability of the leadership, especially at the minimum, to make a calendar decision concerning the development of reality or the adoption of modern trends.

There were statistically significant differences between the average responses of the university leadership sample, depending on the variable of specialization, and the identification of the reality of the university's exercise of its responsibilities towards environmental sustainability and environmental greening as a whole, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Differences in statistical indications between sample responses to determine the realities of the university's practices for its responsibilities towards sustainability and environmental greening

Variables		Axle A		
		Mean	F	Sig.
Specialization	Islamic Science	22.9	8.241	0.000
	Human Sciences	19.33		
	Natural Science	23.88		
Leadership position	Dean	19.74	1.979	0.141
	Associate Dean	22.80		
	Head of the Dep.	29.57		
Degree	Professor	20.05	1.115	0.330
Variables		Axle B		
		Mean	F	Sig.
Specialization	Islamic Science	23.50	6.857	0.001
	Human Sciences	29.56		
	Natural Science	25.40		
Leadership position	Dean	20.45	2.061	0.130
	Associate Dean	24.06		
	Head of the Dep.	21.99		
Degree	Professor	21.89	0.596	0.552
Variables		Axle C		
		Mean	F	Sig.
Specialization	Islamic Science	20.30	3.978	0.020
	Human Sciences	17.96		
	Natural Science	21.28		
Leadership position	Dean	18.12	1.118	0.329
	Associate Dean	20.49		
	Head of the Dep.	18.87		
Degree	Professor	19.37	0.423	0.656
Variables		Axle D		
		Mean	F	Sig.
Specialization	Islamic Science	21.40	5.470	0.005
	Human Sciences	18.29		
	Natural Science	22.23		
Leadership position	Dean	18.02	2.826	0.062
	Associate Dean	21.94		
	Head of the Dep.	19.39		
Degree	Professor	19.03	0.914	0.403
Variables		Total		
		Mean	F	Sig.
Specialization	Islamic Science	88.10	6.625	0.002
	Human Sciences	76.14		
	Natural Science	92.79		

Leadership position	Dean	76.33	2.131	0.122
	Associate Dean	89.29		
	Head of the Dep.	80.82		
Degree	Professor	80.34	0.722	0.487

6. Conclusions

Considering the role of environmental greening in the strategic performance of universities, it is essential to study and extrapolate the views of the leaders at Samarra University on the most important responsibilities assigned to the university. Additionally, understanding the reality of how the university exercises its responsibilities towards environmental greening is crucial. The findings suggest that the university's current commitment to environmental sustainability is only at a modest level. This may be due to the fact that Samarra University is still in the early stages of implementing sustainability and environmental greening initiatives. Several obstacles may be hindering progress, including restrictive university regulations, a lack of strategic vision for environmental sustainability, and insufficient financial and human resources to support a shift towards environmental greening.

Moreover, it is evident that there are statistically significant differences in attitudes towards environmental greening, particularly among those in natural sciences. This correlation may be attributed to the inherent link between natural sciences and environmental greening practices.

To ensure the effective implementation of environmental greening systems at Iraqi universities in general, and Samarra University in particular, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Enhance campus sustainability: The University should transform its campus into a model for sustainable environmental practices. This includes implementing comprehensive waste recycling systems, adhering to policies that promote the construction of green buildings and laboratories, providing sustainable transportation options, reducing energy consumption, rationalizing water usage, and prioritizing the purchase of sustainable products.

2. Promote global sustainable leadership: Universities should be guided towards achieving a classification that reflects a sustainable global dimension in their practices. Increasing community awareness of environmental issues and their impacts on various aspects of life is also vital.

3. Integrate environmental education: Education objectives should be focused on equipping learners with the knowledge, values, and skills necessary for sustainability and environmental greening. The aim is to develop responsible citizens capable of managing environmental resources judiciously, promoting societal health and well-being, and ensuring equitable use of resources without disrupting ecological balance or compromising the rights of future generations. Universities should consider introducing or enhancing courses on sustainability and environmental greening, either as standalone subjects or integrated into existing programs. These courses would educate students and the wider community about the challenges and opportunities related to sustainability.

4. Encourage research and innovation: Investment in the creative potential of researchers is crucial. Directing research towards innovative solutions that reduce carbon emissions, promote environmentally friendly industries, minimize threats to wildlife and marine ecosystems, and combat environmental crimes such as deforestation and overfishing is essential. Efforts should be made to conserve biodiversity and natural resources through the use of environmental databases to classify and protect species, and to intensify research on conserving genetic assets

and protecting endangered species. Other important areas include addressing climate change, improving vegetation cover, exploring alternative energy sources, managing water effectively, and pursuing other environmental sustainability goals and indicators.

These initiatives will not only enhance the environmental performance of Samarra University but also position it as a leader in sustainable practices, contributing positively to community well-being and environmental stewardship.

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